

Real-time obstacle avoidance algorithm and coordination motion strategy for a redundant dual-arm robot

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Abstract: Redundant dual-arm robots provide an effective strategy for the automated achievement of complex assembly operations. Moreover, being kinematically redundant, they simultaneously perform numerous tasks with different priorities. The principal task, obstacle avoidance is generally used as a subtask mainly when the robot is interacting with humans. This paper presents a real-time obstacle avoidance algorithm based on the self-motion characteristic of a redundant dual-arm robot, solving the problem of collision between environmental obstacles and manipulators during operation. The method leans on the gradient "projection method", obtaining the shortest distance between the middle of the obstacle and the connecting rod axis of the two arms in the environment. Moreover, two obstacle avoidance factors are introduced to change the manipulator avoidance speed in real-time; then, the workability of the dual-arm robot is ameliorated increasing the robot's efficiency. By establishing the absolute and relative pose variables, the stability of the two arms during the cooperative task operation is defined, making the problem of self-collision avoidance in the working environment continuous and smooth. The simulation experiment verifies the practicability and efficacy of the proposed algorithm

Keywords: Redundant dual-arm robot; Real-time obstacle avoidance; Coordinated operation

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Introduction

Redundant dual-arm robots compared with non-redundant robots are characterized by good fault tolerance, wider applicability, better dexterity, and so on[1] [2]. Because of the fact that the robot is kinetically redundant, it is capable of moving the end-effector through the same trajectory with the help of various mechanical structure configurations, performing the secondary optimization of kinematics and dynamics while executing the cooperative tasks[3]. Considering the implication of robots that are more and more used to execute some complex tasks, it is important to take into account the safety of the robot. That brings the means to resolve some complex motion tasks, like the avoidance

of obstacles between the robot and the working environment and also avoiding the collision of the dual-arm robot when working in coordination [4].

The collision avoidance tasks are fundamentally considered as a path planning robot problem[5] which is why many works have been done in this way to find some classic methods. That is the case of Khatib, who profoundly worked on the inverse kinematic second-order torque and acceleration that enhance the use of the robot intelligence in order to perform some complex tasks, and also takes into account the security of the robot while working [6]. Redundant manipulators can perform the obstacle avoidance task using two main directions, which are global and local path planning [7]. Concerning real-time obstacle avoidance, local path planning is preferred over the global one, in fact, its algorithm is less computationally intensive and relies on some visual sensors in order to obtain real-time, information about the position of the obstacles in the working environment [8].

Nowadays, researchers at home and abroad are studying the methods of obstacle avoidance for redundant robots principally by considering a single-arm robot as the research object [9], [10]. Kinetically, it is important to take into account the collision avoidance path planning between the two robotics manipulators [11], [12], and dynamically it is necessary to coordinate the redundant dual-arm robot end-effector while performing cooperative tasks [13], [14]. Logically, these cause the mishap of the control system, so while avoiding the collision between the robot, the work environment, and the robot arm coordination, it is necessary to focus on the problem of colliding between the two manipulators [15] or between the robot and the environmental obstacle[16]. There exist quite a few studies that consider both of these two situations.

Therefore, a real-time obstacle avoidance algorithm based on the self-motion characteristic of redundant manipulators is proposed in this paper. At first, it is preferable to carry out the position relationship between the obstacle, the robot, and the arms. After that, to judge the pole that is subject to collision in order to complete the action of obstacle avoidance. Thus, a pre-screening vector projection is built to explain its construction process. Secondly, the kinematics inverse solution regarding the du-al-arm avoiding the obstacle in the cooperative task is discussed aiming to change the speed of the nearest point of the obstacle on the manipulator in real-time, so that the manipulator can avoid the obstacle continuously and smoothly. Then, the gradient safe distance is used to evaluate the degree of collision separating the robot's two arms, and also separating the robot's arms and the environmental obstacle.

2. Description of the Redundant Dual-Arm robot:

The robot used for the research experiment is the MOTOMAN-SDA10 as expressed in figure 1, which is a redundant spatial dual-arm robot. It is made up of two serial manipulators with seven degrees of freedom. The left arm is the secondary arm and the right one is the primary arm, and the configuration and dimension as shown in figure 2, are from the universal description format (SDA20F) file committed for the MOTOMAN-SDA10 [17]. The mathematical model of the redundant dual-arm robot shown in figure 3, is built from MATLAB/Robotic toolbox.

Fig. 1: Redundant Dual-Arm robot

Fig. 2: Redundant Dual-Arm Robot structure diagram

Fig. 3: Mathematical model of the Redundant Dual-Arm Robot.

3-Shortest distance calculation:

Most of the actual methods doing the obstacle avoidance of manipulators, consider the redundant robot as a piece-wise line and then use the gradient projection method to calculate the obstacle and the manipulators' shortest distance[18]. The piece-wise line method only takes into account the length factor of the manipulators and ignores its volume factor, which is sometimes the main failure reason for obstacle avoidance in the actual operation. However, it is necessary to fully consider the overall volume size of the manipulators and then calculate the actual nearest distance between the manipulators and the obstacle, then plan the algorithm for avoiding the obstacle of the redundant dual-arm robot.

Taking into consideration the limitation of the above indicators, this paper put forward a method to pre-screen the projection vector parameters, firstly the manipulators are shortened through the envelope capsule method and the obstacle is a spherical envelope. Secondly, before finding the shortest distance between the link of the robot and the obstacle, the projection of the obstacle on the robot's members is first calculated. Some rods that will not come into the collision are approximately selected and moreover, the shortest distance between the bars that shall collide with the obstacle is calculated to reduce some unessential calculations.

3.1- Shortest distance calculation based on gradient projection method:

When the manipulators are in a coordinated operation, the connecting rods of the primary and secondary manipulator will be considered obstacles to each other. Aiming to avoid a self-collision problem, it is important to calculate in real time when the secondary manipulator is an obstacle to the main arm. Moreover, the shortest distance from each link of the primary arm to the secondary arm must be calculated, and at the same time, in order to avoid collision with the environmental obstacles, the environmental obstacles are projected to the primary and secondary manipulators so that the shortest distance between the environmental obstacles together with the primary and secondary manipulator in real time could be obtained. The i connecting rod of the primary arm, the j connecting rod of the secondary arm, and the environmental obstacle k are taken as the research objects, and the position relationship is set as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: The positional relationship between the i -th link of the primary arm, and the j -th link of the secondary arm, and the environmental obstacle diagram

3.2- The shortest distance between the primary arm rod i and the environmental obstacle k :

The geometric relationship between the primary arm i -th connecting rod and the environmental obstacle k is shown in Figure 5. Points A_i and B_i represent the initial joint and the end joint of the i -th connecting rod of the primary arm, respectively. Their position vectors in the robotic reference coordinate system $O_B - X_B Y_B Z_B$ are the length of i -th connecting rod in the capsule surround model of the main arm of C, d, l_i , respectively. Then the unit vector of the i -th connecting rod of the primary arm is expressed as:

$$e_i = \frac{d - c}{l_i} \tag{1}$$

The position of the point F_{ik} with the shortest distance of the i -th axis connecting rod of the primary arm and obstacle k is related to the positive and negative projection β_{ik} of the obstacle k on the axis of the i -th connecting rod of the primary arm.

$$\beta_{i_1} = e_i^T (t - c) \tag{2}$$

e_i^T is the transposition of e_i , t is the vector position of the obstacle center k in the reference frame $O_B - X_B Y_B Z_B$.

So, the position vector G of F_{ik} , the shortest point from obstacle k on the axis of link i of the primary arm in the reference coordinate system is:

$$G = \begin{cases} c & ; \quad \beta_i < 0 \\ c + \beta_i e_i & ; \quad 0 < \beta_i < l_i \\ d & ; \quad \beta_i > l_i \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Therefore, the nearest distance between the center of environmental obstacle k and i -th connecting rod axis of the primary arm is:

$$d_{ik} = \|G - t\| \tag{4}$$

$\|\cdot\|$ represents the module of the vector, and considering the influence of the actual manipulator model and the volume factor of the environmental obstacle, the nearest distance between the environmental obstacle k and the link i of the primary arm is modified to:

$$D_{ik} = d_{ik} - R_i - R_k \tag{5}$$

R_i is the radius of the i -th connecting rod of the primary arm in the simplified model of the dual-arm manipulator's capsule, is the environmental obstacle k radius.

Fig. 5: Geometric relationship the i -th link of the primary arm and the environmental obstacle k .

3.3- Calculation of the nearest distance between the primary arm connecting rod i and the j :

When the primary arm and the secondary arm coordinately transport the object, the obstacle that the j - link of the secondary arm looks toward is the i -link of the secondary arm and it is analyzed. Then, the position and attitude of the j - link of the secondary arm are calculated by the initial joint and the joint end regarding to the j - link of the secondary arm. The geometric relationship between the i - link of the primary arm and the j - link of the secondary arm is shown in Figure 6. C_i and D_j are the initial joint and end joint of the j - link , with their position vectors in the robot reference coordinate system $O_B-X_{BY}Z_{B'}$, respectively h and m . F_{ij2} is the shortest point on the axis of the primary arm i connecting rod, from the starting joint of the j connecting rod of the secondary arm, and F_{ij3} is the shortest point on the end joint of the j connecting rod of the primary arm. The position vectors of the robot reference coordinate system are respectively r and s .

Fig. 6: Geometric relationship connecting the i -th and the j -th link of the primary and secondary arm.

The starting joint of the j -th connecting rod of the secondary arm is regarded as the obstacle of the i -th connecting rod of the primary arm, and at this time:

$$\beta_{ij2} = e_i^T (h - c) \tag{6}$$

β_{ij2} represents the projection from the j -th link on the i -th link axis of the primary arm. According to the method in formulas (5) and (1), the shortest distance from the axis of the i -th connecting rod of the primary arm to the starting joint of the j -th connecting rod of the secondary arm.

$$d_{ij2} = \|r - h\| \tag{7}$$

Considering the volume factor of the secondary arm, the shortest distance between the i -th link of the primary arm and the starting joint of the j -th link of the secondary arm is modified to:

$$D_{ij2} = d_{ij2} - R_i - R_j \tag{8}$$

R_j is the radius of the j -th of the primary arm in the simplified capsule model of a redundant dual-arm manipulators. If the end joint of the j -th arm is regarded as the obstacle of the i -th of the primary arm, then:

$$\beta_{ij3} = e_i^T (m - c) \tag{9}$$

β_{ij3} is the projection of the end joint of the j -th link from the i -th link axis of the primary arm. Similarly, the nearest distance of the i -th link axis separating the primary arm and the end joint of the j -th link from the secondary arm can be obtained:

$$d_{ij3} = \|s - m\| \tag{10}$$

Considering the volume factor of the secondary arm, the shortest distance between the i -th axis of the primary arm and the end joint of the j -th of the secondary arm is:

$$D_{ij3} = d_{ij3} - R_i - R_j \tag{11}$$

Using the above method, the shortest distance of the environmental obstacle on each link of the primary arm can be obtained.

4 - Obstacle Avoidance Motion Space of Dual-arm Robot:

Generally, the obstacle avoidance task mainly identifies the nearest points on the robot manipulators, then attributes to the manipulators a motion component that moves away those points from the obstacle. On the one hand, the collision avoidance problem could be solved using a global strategy, like high-level path planning, which is seen as a planning problem and assure to research a free path collision from the starting to the terminal point (either that point exists). Moreover, the fact that this method is generally not dependent on any sensor feedback information, they are merely convenient for well specify environment.

On the other hand, the local strategy could be an excellent way to solve this problem in considering the avoidance task like a control problem. The goal of this method is not to replace the high-level free path collision, but make use of the low-level control. Contrarily to the global methods, they can rely on the feedback information coming from sensors so as to modify the path whether the obstacle moves or figures in the environment. In addition, the local strategy is mainly appropriated when one cannot find the position of the obstacle in advance. In fact, through that method the obstacle position can be obtained in real-time while executing the task, making the above mentioned the main reasons to utilize this method for the online collision avoidance, especially in an unstructured environment.

During the cooperative operation between the dual-arm of the space robot, the motion of the robot is a three-dimensional space movement. The avoiding task motion follow the direction of the dual-arm robot corresponding to the mark point that is a straight-line direction through the obstacle center referring to the marker point. Then, the movement of avoiding obstacle is reduced to a one-dimensional space movement, enhancing then the calculation accuracy and at the same time reducing the amount of calculation.

So, the primary arm of the robot is taken as an example and at the moment that the obstacle of the secondary arm of the robot is the primary arm, the obstacle avoidance direction of the marker point of the primary arm is solved. At first, the equations (1) to (11) corresponding to each member of the primary arm in order to get the distance between each link of the primary arm and the obstacle (including the environment obstacle and the secondary arm). By judging the size of each distance, the shortest distance corresponds to the position of the mark point on the robotic arms as show in figure 7.

Figure 7. Dual-arm robot obstacle avoidance motion diagram.

The marking point is the shortest point to the obstacle on each bar of the robot.

The obstacle avoidance movement only needs the marking points to move along the straight line connecting to the marking point and the nearest point of the obstacle.

The direction of the obstacle avoidance on the primary arm of the robot is described as:

$$\mathbf{n}_{01} = \frac{\mathbf{d}_{01}}{\|\mathbf{d}_{01}\|} \tag{12}$$

The velocity $\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{01}$ and the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{01}}$ of the mark point on the primary arm are:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_{d_{01}} = \mathbf{n}_{01}^T \dot{\mathbf{x}}_{01} \tag{13}$$

$$\mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{01}} = \mathbf{n}_{01}^T \mathbf{J}_{01} \tag{14}$$

In the same way, later when the movement space of the obstacle avoidance is reduced, the velocity $\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{02}$ and the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{02}}$ from the mark point on the secondary arm are:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_{d_{02}} = \mathbf{n}_{02}^T \dot{\mathbf{x}}_{02} \tag{15}$$

$$\mathbf{J}_{\dot{\mathbf{d}}_{02}} = \mathbf{n}_{02}^T \mathbf{J}_{02} \tag{16}$$

4.1 - Time optimal obstacle avoidance method for a redundant robot:

According to the current position of the arms' end, the target point position and the obstacle location, the redundant robot can avoid the obstacle. The primary arm is taken as example to build gravitational and repulsive force vectors by the errors between the current manipulator position, the target's position, and the target of the obstacle position.

Fig. 8: Gravitational repulsion and resultant force vector.

$$P_{att} = k_{att}(p_t - p_e) \quad ; \quad P_{rep} = k_{rep}(p_t - p_{obs})$$

With:
$$\Delta p = P_{rep} + P_{att}$$

Aiming to guarantee the uniformity and stability of terminal velocity, the incrementation of terminal position is normalized. Equation can be arranged as follows:

$$\Delta p = k_s \cdot \frac{k_{att}(p_t - p_e) + k_{rep}(p_t - p_{obs})}{\|k_{att}(p_t - p_e) + k_{rep}(p_t - p_{obs})\|} \tag{17}$$

k_s is the step-size coefficient, the end velocity of the manipulator is defined as the first derivative of the terminal position increment to time.

$$v = \dot{x} = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta t}$$

When the time interval is small enough, the incremental position of the end can be approximated as the end of the arm speed.

$$\dot{x} = \Delta p$$

In order to prevent the end of the robot arm from colliding with the obstacle, the variation of the nearest distance point and the nearest distance separating the obstacle and the connecting rod is considered comprehensively.

The joint velocity could be expressed by the following formula:

$$\dot{q}_1 = J_0^+ \dot{x} = J_0^+ \Delta p \dot{x}_0 \tag{18}$$

J_0 represents the Jacobian matrix representing the nearest distance point of obstacle and bar.

\dot{x}_0 is the speed of motion at the closest point.

J_0^+ represents the pseudo-inverse of a matrix $J_0^+ = J_0^T (J_0 J_0^T)^{-1}$.

4.2- Kinematic constraint equation of the redundant dual-arm robot collaboration:

The relationship between the terminal velocity and the joint velocity for a single arm is expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{P}_i \\ W_i \end{bmatrix} = J_i(q_i) \dot{q} \quad (i = 1, 2) \tag{19}$$

$J_i \in R^{m \times n}$ and \dot{q} are respectively the Jacobian matrix and the joint velocity vector of the robot.

When the redundant dual-arm is transported an object, a closed kinematic chain is formed between the two arms of the robot. The motion of this closed chain must satisfy some kinematics relationship in order to achieve the collaboration task as stated in [19].

So, the absolute kinematic constraint equations between the rigid body and the two arms are expressed as follow:

$$\dot{x}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{P}_0 \\ W_0 \end{bmatrix} = J_0(q_1 \quad q_2) \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{20}$$

\dot{x}_0 expressed the absolute velocity at the center of the rigid body, \dot{P}_0 and W_0 are respectively the absolute linear velocity and angular velocity of the central in the refence coordinate system $O_B - X_B Y_B Z_B$ and $J_0 \in R^{m \times 2n}$ is the Jacobian matrix conforming to the absolute motion of the operating target.

Similarly, the relative kinematic constraint equation between the rigid body and the two arms of the robot is:

$$\dot{x}_r = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{P}_r \\ W_r \end{bmatrix} = J_r(q_1 \quad q_2) \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{21}$$

With \dot{x}_r the relative velocity at the center of the rigid body $J_r = [-J_1 \quad J_2]^T$ $J_r \in R^{m \times 2n}$ represents the Jacobian matrix relating to the relative motion of two arms.

Then the kinematic equations of the redundant two-arm robot are obtained by combining the equations (20) and (21).

$$\dot{x} = J(q_1 \quad q_2) \dot{q} \tag{22}$$

$x = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_0 \\ \dot{x}_r \end{bmatrix}^T$ Represents the dual-arm robot end velocity.

$$J(q_1 \quad q_2) = \begin{bmatrix} J_0(q_1 \quad q_2) \\ J_r(q_1 \quad q_2) \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Represents the speed Jacobian matrix for the double arm coordinated operation}$$

$$\dot{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_1 \\ \dot{q}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Represents the angular vector velocity of the dual-arm robot.}$$

There are many solutions to the joint velocity that can introduce the corresponding constraint conditions in order to achieve the second goal, such as obstacle avoidance.

5 – Real time obstacle avoidance algorithm for redundant dual-arm robot cooperative strategy:

The problem of avoiding obstacle for redundant dual-arm manipulators requires that the components of the two manipulators will not collide with obstacles while completing the coordination task.

Based on (22), the inverse kinematics solution to the problem can be obtained by improving the obstacle avoidance algorithm of the dual-arm redundant robot.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q} = \dot{q}_1 + (J_{1d_{01}} N)^+ (\dot{x}_{1d_{01}} - J_{1d_{01}} J^+ \dot{x}) \\ + (J_{2d_{02}} N)^+ (\dot{x}_{2d_{02}} - J_{2d_{02}} J^+ \dot{x}) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Based on (18):
$$\dot{q}_1 = k_s \cdot J_0^+ \frac{k_{att}(p_t - p_e) + k_{rep}(p_t - p_{obs})}{\|k_{att}(p_t - p_e) + k_{rep}(p_t - p_{obs})\|} \dot{x}_0$$

Where:
$$\dot{x}_0 = \frac{v_m}{2d_0} \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi d_0}{d_m}\right) + 1 \right] (x_{obs} - x_B, y_{obs} - y_B, z_{obs} - z_B)$$

And (x_B, y_B, z_B) is the nearest point coordinate, $(x_{obs}, y_{obs}, z_{obs})$ represents the location point coordinate.

$J_{1d_{01}}$ and $\dot{x}_{1d_{01}}$ represent the Jacobian matrix of the motion of the marker point closest to the obstacle on the manipulator 1 and the velocity vector of the movement of that marker point, respectively.

$J_{2d_{02}}$ and $\dot{x}_{2d_{02}}$ represent the Jacobian matrix of the motion of the marker point closest to the obstacle on the manipulator 2 and the velocity vector of the movement of that marker point, respectively.

The sign "+" denotes finding the Generalized Inverses of Moore-Penrose Matrices and $N = I - J^+ J$ is the zero space of the Jacobian matrix describing the coordinated manipulation motion of the arms and is the unit matrix.

The trajectory planning algorithm of the dual-arm redundant robot based on the task priority steps are summarized in flowchart as shown in figure 6.

Figure 9: Dual-arm robot flow chart of the trajectory planning based on the task priority

Aiming to efficiently control the robot's arms in order to avoid obstacles and guarantee its cooperative task, two obstacles avoidance factors are introduced:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q} = \dot{q}_1 + \alpha_1 \left(J_{1d_{01}} N \right)^+ \left(\gamma_1 \dot{x}_{1d_{01}} - J_{1d_{01}} J^+ \dot{x} \right) \\ + \alpha_2 \left(J_{2d_{02}} N \right)^+ \left(\gamma_2 \dot{x}_{2d_{02}} - J_{2d_{02}} J^+ \dot{x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

α_1 , α_2 , represent the joint angular velocity factors, respectively and γ_1 , γ_2 , are the speed factors of obstacle avoidance at the primary and secondary arms respectively.

Introducing gradient "safe distance" $d_n = (1, 2, 3)$ ensures the smoothness and continuity of motion of the two arms in obstacle avoidance.

The relationship between α_1 , α_2 , γ_1, γ_2 , and d_n is:

$$\alpha_{1,2}(d_{oi}) = \begin{cases} 1 & d_1 < d_{oi} < d_2 \\ b_0 + b_1 d_{oi} + b_2 d_{oi}^2 + b_3 d_{oi}^3 & d_2 < d_{oi} < d_3 \\ 0 & d_{oi} > d_3 \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

$$\gamma_{1,2}(d_{oi}) = \begin{cases} E_0 + E_1 d_{oi} + E_2 d_{oi}^2 & d_1 \leq d_{oi} < d_2 \\ 0 & d_2 \leq d_{oi} < d_3 \\ 0 & d_{oi} \geq d_3 \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

$$b_0 = \frac{-d_3^3 + 3d_2 d_3^3}{d_2^3 - 3d_2^2 d_3 + 3d_2 d_3^2 - d_3^3}; \quad b_1 = \frac{-d_3^3 + 3d_2 d_3^3}{d_2^3 - 3d_2^2 d_3 + 3d_2 d_3^2 - d_3^3}; \quad b_2 = \frac{3(d_1 + d_2)}{d_2^3 - 3d_2^2 d_3 + 3d_2 d_3^2 - d_3^3}$$

$$b_3 = \frac{-2}{d_2^3 - 3d_2^2 d_3 + 3d_2 d_3^2 - d_3^3}; \quad E_0 = \frac{U d_2^3}{(d_1 - d_2)^2}; \quad E_1 = \frac{-2U d_2}{(d_1 - d_2)^2}; \quad E_2 = \frac{U}{(d_1 - d_2)^2}$$

The relationship between $\alpha_1, \gamma_1, \alpha_2, \gamma_2$ and the gradient "safe distance" d_n is shown in figure 6.

Figure 10. Relationship between α, γ and the safety distance.

Noting that, when the distance between the marker points on the robot arm and the obstacle $d_{oi} > d_3$, it is the safe stage, the obstacle has no effect on the motion of the robot, and the robot does not produce the obstacle avoidance motion.

Replacing (24) by:
$$\dot{q} = J^+ \dot{x} \quad (27)$$

When the distance between the marker points on the robotic arms and the obstacle $d_2 < d_{oi} < d_3$, In this case γ is zero and α is increased gradually from zero.

$$\dot{q} = \dot{q}_1 - \alpha_1 \left(J_{1d_{o1}} N \right)^+ \left(J_{1d_{o1}} J^+ \dot{x} \right) - \alpha_2 \left(J_{2d_{o2}} N \right)^+ \left(J_{2d_{o2}} J^+ \dot{x} \right) \quad (28)$$

When the distance between the marker on the arms and the obstacle $d_1 < d_{oi} < d_2$ it is a dangerous stage. As the manipulators gets closer to the obstacle, the obstacle avoidance speed factor γ of the mark points on the manipulators

gradually becomes larger, making the manipulators move faster to avoid the obstacle. When d_{io} falls to d_1 , then \mathcal{V} reaches the set maximum value. Then replacing (29) by:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q} = \dot{q}_1 + \alpha_1 \left(J_{1d_{01}} N \right)^+ \left(\mathcal{V}_1 \dot{x}_{1d_{01}} - J_{1d_{01}} J^+ \dot{x} \right) \\ + \alpha_2 \left(J_{2d_{02}} N \right)^+ \left(\mathcal{V}_2 \dot{x}_{2d_{02}} - J_{2d_{02}} J^+ \dot{x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Fig. 11 represents a redundant planar dual-arm robot took as research object. The reference coordinate system of the redundant planar robot corresponding to the primary arm and secondary arm are respectively $O_{1.4} - X_{1.4}Y_{1.4}$ and $O_{2.4} - X_{2.4}Y_{2.4}$.

Besides, l_{1i} and l_{2i} represent the lengths of the i link of the primary and secondary arm, also q_{1i} and q_{2i} are the rotational joint angles of the i -th links of both two arms ($i = 1,2,3,4$). The symbol “+” denotes the positive direction of the rotational joint.

Figure 11. Planar redundant dual-arm robot

6 – Simulation and Analysis:

Testing the feasibility of the algorithm, the proposed method is applied to a redundant dual-arm robot with four degrees of freedom as shown in fig. 11 then, MATLAB/Simulink[20] is used for the obstacle avoidance experiment.

Table 1. Specification of the robot.

Connecting rod	Angle variable	Length
n	θ_n	a_n
1	θ_1	l_1
2	θ_2	l_2
3	θ_3	l_3
4	θ_4	l_4

The information contains in the table 1 is not insert to the redundant dual-arm robot. The robot was implemented as expressed in the flow chart at the fig. 9, using as step length coefficient $k_s=7$ mm, the gravity coefficient $k_{att} = 1$ mm, the repulsion coefficient $k_{rep} = 4$ mm. For the reason that the experiment was controlled in simulation, it was unnecessary to use the camera in order to obtain the position of the obstacle in real time. Alternatively, this simulation was carried out internally by the simulator.

Concerning the redundant dual-arm robot, the robot cooperative task here is to use the end-effector of both arms to hold a rigid object, after that to shift the rigid object from a starting position of (0 , 460) mm to an end position (0 , 280) mm. Adding to that the position of environmental obstacle inside of the collaborative space which are (-140 , 190) mm and (114 , 158) mm, in the simulation environment the length of each arm of the robot is set as $l_{11} = l_{21} = 120$ mm; $l_{12} = l_{22} = 140$ mm; $l_{13} = l_{23} = 150$ mm; $l_{14} = l_{24} = 60$ mm and the initial rotation angles corresponding to each joint of the dual-arm robot is respectively: $q_{11} = 60^\circ$; $q_{12} = 40^\circ$; $q_{13} = -30^\circ$; $q_{14} = -60^\circ$; $q_{21} = 120^\circ$; $q_{22} = -40^\circ$; $q_{23} = 30^\circ$; $q_{24} = -60^\circ$, and the parameters of the simplified model of the capsule body of the redundant planar dual-arm robot parameters are: $R_{11} = R_{21} = 10$ mm; $R_{12} = R_{22} = 8$ mm; $R_{13} = R_{23} = 8$ mm; $R_{14} = R_{24} = 6$ mm. Also, the speed of the marker points on the robotic arm to avoid obstacles are 8 and the gradient safe distance is $d_1 = 30$ mm; $d_2 = 22$ mm; $d_3 = 20$ mm.

The Fig. 12 gives the information that at the time t from 0s to 1,6 s the end of the robot arms is moving along the desired trajectory, and at the time t between 1,7s and 6,7s the tracking error exists. Notifying that, at the time t reaching 3,4 s, the maximum trajectory tracking error is 27mm, meaning that at this point, the arms cannot move along the desired trajectory. It can be explained by the fact that the obstacle and the target point have repulsive force and gravitational force respectively on the robot, so under the combined action of the two, the position increment is then obtained.

Fig. 12: The linear tracking error curve.

The Figure 13 then describes the changes of the angular joint as well as the angular velocity and the end position of the robot while in movement. The figures express that when the shortest distance between the members and the obstacle is greater than the safety threshold one, that is to say, when the time t between 0s and 1.6s, the joint angle, the angular velocity, and the end position curve of the robot change smoothly. Besides, when the shortest distance between the bars and the obstacle is less than the safety threshold, that is when the time t is between 1.6s and 6.7s, in order to avoid the obstacle, the joint angles and the manipulators terminal position change in an abrupt way and then appears the inflection point. Finally, at $t = 6.8$ s, the shortest distance between the obstacle and bars gradually exceeds the safety threshold, and the joint angular velocity curve stays stable until the end, then reach the target position. The simulation results show that the proposed algorithm is feasible and effective.

Fig. 13: Joint angular velocity change of the robot arm using obstacle avoidance algorithm of multitask switching.

The fig. 14 is describing the variation of the shortest distance between the redundant robot two arms, the obstacle (together with the environmental obstacles) and the position of the dual-arm with one another.

Fig. 14: The shortest distance between the dual-arm robot and the obstacle.

7- Conclusion:

Based on the complexity of the working space in which the redundant dual-arm robot is operating, a path planning cooperative algorithm is proposed in order to avoid obstacles. Using the projection index vector pre-screening, the probable colliding members in the manipulator can be identified, reducing the volume of calculation, and the nearest distance between the members that could probably collide with the rest of the manipulator and the environmental obstacles can be calculated in real-time. In solving the obstacle avoidance problem, the absolute and relative pose variables are brought forward, defining the coordinated task operation. Besides, when the shortest distance separating the obstacle and the bar is less than the threshold distance, the obstacle avoidance movement is first considered. Comparing then with the gradient "safe distance", the collision danger degree between the manipulator and obstacles is judged. At the same time, the avoidance speed of the manipulator mark points can be modified in real-time. Finally, through simulation, the results prove that the proposed algorithm can resolve the problem of collision between obstacle and terminal trajectory and that the desired trajectory can be tracked after avoiding the obstacle. Besides, the validity of the proposed method was tested by simulating the redundant robot 100 times casual and haphazard target poses laying inside the redundant robot working space, that are feasible by a series of configurations of the robot. Then the robot successfully copes to achieve the task 83% of the time in 100 steps.

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